

Embracing the Complexity of '100% OA'

From Percentage to Participation

Introduction

The Progress and the Plateau

The open access movement has achieved remarkable progress over two decades, reaching over 50% of research articles and conference papers by 2023. Yet, we now face a new challenge: growth is slowing, and the remaining transition appears more complex than the progress achieved so far. As highlighted in the [OASPA Project Primer 'Setting the stage for a 'different conversation' about open access'](#), this inflection point demands reflection. When a community that has spent years building consensus suddenly lacks clear answers about next steps, it's a sign the questions have changed.

'How' Matters More than 'What'

Covering similar themes as the three ['Next 50%' workshops](#) held in June, [OASPA's 2025 Conference](#) explored what comes next—not just counting remaining percentage points, but understanding what they represent. A particularly telling observation emerged: **how** open access is achieved matters, not simply **what** percentage we reach. This reflects sophistication: the values and approaches underlying our work matter as much as the tactics themselves. Polling at the OASPA Conference (see Figure 1) identified key priorities to achieve a global transition to full open access, with the top three being removing barriers so all scholars, worldwide, can publish and share openly; enabling open access for every subject area; and enabling scholarly communication for (and

between) speakers of different languages. These priorities share a fundamental thread: they're about participation and go beyond the long-standing focus on access. They align with what Pinfield describes as "[participatory openness](#)"—enabling diverse contributions from a wide range of actors—which is distinct from making scholarly content freely available to read and reuse. Overall, these are challenges that our current approaches to open access weren't designed to address: success in achieving over 50% has revealed the limitations of today's business-as-usual.

The Challenge Ahead

This position paper acknowledges an uncomfortable tension: any solutions that we can hypothesise today feel uncertain because we face problems that operate at different scales (see Figure 2), require different types of interventions and exceed any single organisation's capacity to solve. The distributed support across multiple areas for action in our conference polling—rather than convergence on one clear path—reflects that the open access community does strive to achieve 100% open access, but consensus is limited on how to get there. We believe that OASPA's role in this context is not to prescribe solutions, but to create the conditions needed for diverse stakeholders in the field to work through uncertainty together. This position paper outlines how we propose to do that.

Figure 1. Responses to the question: 'Which of these aspects should be prioritised to achieve a global transition to full open access? Please pick your top 3 recommendations.' (Source: OASPA Conference 2025, n=87)

Figure 2. The biggest unsolved problems in open access (source: Feedback provided by 2025 OASPA Conference attendees as part of the registration poll; n=107 responses across 26 countries).

Inequity in Publishing Models

Models that distinguish between those with and without access to funds create financial and cultural barriers that limit participation across disciplines, regions, and publisher types.

Limited availability of Sustainable Funding

Existing funding models cannot support a system that is equitable for all stakeholders and contexts. There is a need for new approaches to resourcing scholarly communication, not simply more money.

Excessive focus on Research Articles

Career progression systems favour publishing in high-impact journals, with open access playing a limited role. Most evaluation frameworks also prioritise citation metrics and journal prestige.

Commodification of Research Outputs

Publication is positioned as the final product of research as opposed to researchers and all their working processes being part of an open, ongoing process of knowledge exchange.

Need for more Coordinated Action

There is no clear vision or strategy that unites disparate stakeholders in pursuit of common goals while upholding diversity across regions, contexts and varied approaches to open access.

Three Interlocking Barriers

Input made in response to the project primer (via an online survey and subsequent workshops) and feedback at the OASPA 2025 Conference highlighted three interconnected challenges that limit participation in scholarly publishing.

1. Geographic and Economic Exclusion

Greater access to published content has not automatically translated to greater participation in knowledge production. Initiatives such as Research4Life have expanded reading access to researchers in lower-income countries; yet, as Powell et al. observe, "the contribution made by researchers in its eligible countries as authors, editors and peer reviewers remains low."

The infrastructure that enables some institutions to publish at scale can simultaneously reinforce existing disparities. Mature open access ecosystems in regions like Latin America and Indonesia—which prioritise free access for both authors and readers—remain largely invisible to bibliometric databases which are often relied on for research evaluation and researcher career progression, creating a false impression of Global North dominance in scholarly communication. The initiatives and organisations that are most critical to inclusion and representation may count themselves among the most precarious and least visible initiatives, regardless of location.

2. Disciplinary Fragmentation

Although over 50% of research articles and conference papers are available via open access, the figure for monographs and books is only 18% as of 2023, as discussed in our project primer.

This is just one indicator of different disciplinary publishing cultures, evaluation systems and reader expectations. Scholars in the humanities and social sciences often depend on long-form outputs and face different incentive structures to their STEM counterparts. There is also significant variation across STEM subjects (e.g. practices vary between physics, chemistry, mathematics and biomedicine).

Article processing charges and transformative agreements have achieved significant scale in certain disciplines, but per-output payment models do not work everywhere, particularly for scholars relying on long-form outputs. The challenge is recognising that discipline-specific publishing cultures will require discipline-specific solutions. Such solutions, across a growing spectrum of subjects, approaches and knowledge systems around the world, are also likely to need recognition and enabling of formats other than text- and chapter-based outputs.

3. Linguistic Hegemony

Amano et al document that "non-native English speakers, especially those of low English proficiency nationalities, are more likely to have their papers rejected by journals due to English writing, compared to native English speakers." This creates compounding disadvantages: researchers from non-English-speaking regions face higher barriers to publication, which then affects their career advancement and institutional standing, which further limits their resources to overcome language barriers. Robust regional publishing infrastructures exist but cross-language integration is rare. When 'international' bibliometric databases exclude non-English outputs, they don't simply create data gaps—they reinforce the perception that valuable scholarship only happens in English, in indexed venues, following Western academic conventions.

The Deeper Pattern

These challenges are manifestations of a publishing system that has been optimised for scale, efficiency and standardisation rather than diversity, inclusion and contextual relevance. Progress to date in making a greater proportion of research freely available online has exposed these deeper structural issues. The conference feedback confirms that stakeholders recognise this pattern. The emphasis on enabling participation across regions, subjects and languages reflects an understanding that removing paywalls, while necessary, is insufficient for truly equitable open access.

Why Solutions Remain Uncertain

No Single Organisation Has all the Answers

At the 2025 OASPA Conference, the next steps felt fuzzy, because the problems discussed:

- operate at different scales of intervention;
- involve different types of actors; and
- require sustained coordinated action over time.

One conference participant observed that perhaps "strengthening the commons" is fundamental, pointing to the insight that infrastructure and values may need attention before tactical interventions can succeed.

Yet, the lack of clear consensus in the conference polling reveals that the field itself is uncertain about which levers to pull next. We propose to organise the challenge into two categories.

First, **system-level challenges** require coordinated action across stakeholder types and often involve changing structures outside the publishing system. Coordinated action could achieve outcomes such as:

- Research evaluation frameworks that privilege methodological diversity and community impact (rather than publication quantity or citation counts), and that value a diversity of knowledge systems, including indigenous knowledge
- Funding mechanisms that provide a way to support open access with broad participation and diverse contributions from all scholars
- Diversity of publishing infrastructures that include and involve the scholarly community
- Celebration of open access as a sought-after and trusted practice around the world, with no perceptions or linkages with fraudulent work or the practices of predatory publishers
- Economic structures that close the gaps in South-North disparities in research funding and resources
- Responsible use of technology (e.g. artificial intelligence) in line with the terms of open access licences

Individual organisations can each contribute to these outcomes, but no organisation can achieve them unilaterally.

Second, **sector-level challenges** involve a concerted transformation of publishing practices and infrastructures:

- Business model innovation and diversification beyond dominant models
- Constructive engagement between commercial and non-commercial publishing infrastructures
- Multilingualism, with outputs enabled in a plurality of languages, including fostering exchange between speakers of different languages and developing multilingual indexing and discovery systems
- Standards for representing and validating diverse knowledge systems and output types

Progress here depends on coalition-building, shared experimentation, and coordinated investment.

Opportunities for OASPA

Feedback on our work during the conference highlighted that stakeholders would welcome OASPA's input in convening and guiding discussions.

This helps us identify roles that OASPA can play directly (see shaded box below), as opposed to areas where a greater extent of coordinated action will be needed.

Roles that OASPA can distinctively play within its capacity and remit:

- OASPA as a **facilitator**: Convening cross-stakeholder dialogue on specific challenges, including creating deliberate pathways for mutual visibility between regional and international publishing ecosystems
- OASPA as a **connector**: Bridging perspectives between publishers, libraries, funders and researchers
- OASPA as a **learning network**: Creating structured spaces for experimentation (e.g. workshops, working groups) and sharing insights

From Aspirations to Action

What's at Stake

Without deliberate action to address the structural barriers we have identified and explored, the open access movement risks achieving a hollow victory where only those at well-resourced institutions in English-speaking regions are served. Researchers elsewhere, along with diverse knowledge systems, languages, and disciplinary traditions, would remain invisible or undervalued within such a system. Additionally, achieving open access for the 'final 50%' of research articles (as charted in our [project primer](#)) would likely become increasingly difficult to reach. This would not be due to opposition to openness, but because today's approaches don't fit the contexts where participation is a challenge. Meanwhile, publishers, institutions and funders could keep investing in infrastructure that inadvertently reinforces existing inequalities.

As it was originally envisioned in the [Budapest Open Access Initiative](#), the movement meant to “accelerate research, enrich education, share the learning of the rich with the poor and the poor with the rich, make this literature as useful as it can be, and lay the foundation for uniting humanity in a common intellectual conversation and quest for knowledge.” Today, the cost of inaction isn't just stalled progress, but the potential fragmentation of the open access movement itself, as different stakeholder groups pursue incompatible visions of what a full transition might look like.

The beliefs of Paulo Freire, an educator and well-known social-change activist, are helpful in this context. Paulo philosophised that education does not change the world. Education changes people. People change the world. Applying this wisdom to the open access movement, it is open participation, enabling a fully open knowledge-exchange between all people, that will empower communities to make a better world. As a result, if we don't address how open access is achieved alongside what percentage we reach, we risk losing the trust and engagement of communities whose participation is essential for a meaningful transition.

What OASPA Endeavours to Do Next

Shaped by the insight that **participation** in open access matters just as much as **increasing** open access, our ambitions prioritise approach, values, and process over prescriptive tactics. Our work also reveals that there is no single "right answer" for prioritisation. Rather than treating this as a problem, we recognise it as giving OASPA **both freedom and responsibility** to identify our strategic priorities based on:

- where coordinated action can have direct impact without needing system-wide transformation;
- where we avoid duplicating others' work;
- where we can genuinely engage our stakeholders to generate positive energy and commitment to drive efforts; and
- where we can balance ambition with achievability to maintain momentum and show meaningful results

Translating our aspirations into concrete action requires clear commitments and accountability. To enable this, the following page sets out a roadmap to help shape our upcoming strategic planning cycle.

OASPA envisions that our future efforts will need to encompass:

- Transparent reporting, including regular updates on progress, experiments, and learning, including what isn't working
- Community feedback loops, testing whether our focus areas remain appropriate through convenings, consultations and conversations
- Course correction, so we can stop initiatives that aren't generating value and redirect resources based on emerging evidence
- Honest assessment that distinguishes between activity and impact, between outputs and outcomes

The ‘Different Conversation’

This paper argues that OASPA's contribution to completing the transition to open access lies not in having all the answers, but in creating processes for the community to work through uncertainty together.

Below are our proposed next steps in the short, medium and long term following this consultation:

Short term

- Ensure geographically and model-diverse stakeholders convene to discuss the key topics emerging from our ‘Next 50%’ consultation and the 2025 OASPA Conference (e.g. participation, sustainable funding)
- See growing evidence of cross-stakeholder engagement (not just publishers talking to publishers)
- Broaden OASPA's set of open access publishing tools and resources, with a focus on equitable publishing

Medium term

- Provide specific guidance on implementing equitable practices
- See observable changes in practices, across OASPA members and the wider open access network, based on recommendations
- Find external stakeholders seeking OASPA as a convening partner for specific challenges
- Report on the growing evidence base for what works in specific contexts (not universal prescriptions)

Long term

- OASPA being recognised as the space where commercial and non-commercial actors co-create solutions
- See demonstrable progress on participatory openness metrics (not just % OA)
- See open publishing practices reflecting the values of participation and all ways of knowing

The ‘different conversation’ we are proposing requires:

- Honesty about what we don't know rather than false confidence in prescriptive strategies
- Transparency about constraints as a foundation for realistic goal-setting
- Experimentation and learning as valuable in themselves, not just means to predetermined ends
- Recognition of diverse and contextually-relevant approaches rather than seeking uniformity and standardisation
- Celebrating what we have achieved while recognising where we need to adapt our approaches to move forwards
- Attention to how open access is achieved and who can engage and benefit—focusing on inclusive values and building relationships through open practices

The timeframes and goals on this page represent directional ambitions rather than fixed commitments. They acknowledge that meaningful change requires time to foster relationships, test approaches, and learn from what works in different contexts. OASPA's current strategic cycle comes to a close in 2026, and the waypoints listed on this page provide a bedrock for developing OASPA's new strategic plan.

We believe that success will depend on genuine engagement from across the open access community and our collective willingness to adapt when evidence suggests different approaches might work better.

We therefore present these goals as a way to articulate our intentions, while preserving the flexibility that complex challenges demand.

We invite the open access community to join us in this different conversation—one that values how we get there as much as reaching the destination itself.

Get in Touch

About OASPA

Representing a diverse community of organisations engaged in open scholarship, OASPA works to encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs. We are committed to our mission of developing and disseminating solutions that advance open access and ensuring a diverse, vibrant, and healthy open access community.

www.oaspa.org

Any thoughts? Share your views - good or bad - via [our feedback form](#). Or get in touch via malavika.legge@oaspa.org.

About Research Consulting

Research Consulting is a mission-driven research and scholarly communication consultancy, working with national and international organisations to help them make the most of their research processes and findings. We are active participants in the research ecosystem, and our work covers all aspects of the research life-cycle, including policy, funding, management, publishing and knowledge exchange.

www.research-consulting.com

Get in touch via andrea.chiarelli@research-consulting.com.

Authors: Malavika Legge, David Ross, Andrea Chiarelli, Katie Fraser, Rob Johnson

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